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Joint Convention Balikpapan 2015

HAGI-IAGI-IAFMI-IATMI

5–8 October 2015

The potential of ichnofossil for the interpretation of depositional environment conditions: an example from outcrop studies in Samarinda, Kutai Basin East Kalimantan

Ery Arifullah^{1*}, Yahdi Zaim¹, Aswan¹, Andang Bachtiar²

1) Department of Geology, Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB)

2) GDA Consulting

ABSTRACT

Sedimentological research in the Kutai Basin related to deltaic deposit has been studied since 1970s which lithofacies has been employed as central parameter. However, that has been contrary the fact that ichnofossil has been still paid regardless of fruitful parameter and used solely as attribute of depositional environment analysis by previous workers although they have to record it.

This paper will establish the potential of ichnofossil data to explain the meaning of the cyclical and variability of fluvial influx and marine process based on outcrops studies in Kesejahteraan and Melati Roads, Samarinda City. The use of ichnofossil characteristics (e.g., bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, burrow diameter, burrow lining and penetration depth) as a proxy for the ascertaining the environmental conditions. The significant finding is that environment regularly might have been intruded by various intensities of fluvial influx, thereby fluctuating environmental conditions such as salinity, water turbidity, oxygenation, sediment stability. That of environment did not compel the depositional environment is changing but manifested the short lived construction in the delta formation.

The proposal of various deltaic processes is rather more conjectural in spite of the fact that limited ichnofossil data can make a difference in understanding. The enforcement of ichnological analysis is required to accomplish the rigorous interpretation.

Keywords: ichnofossil, ichnofabric, fluvial, wave, storm, tidal, short lived construction.

INTRODUCTION

Deltaic origin of the Miocene in the Kutai Basin is a consensus among sedimentary geologist in Indonesia. This is a reasonable viewpoint because of regional and

local tectonic setting triggered potentially deltaic formation in the Miocene to present (Samuel and Muchsin, 1975; Rose and Hartono, 1978; Nuay, et al. 1985; Moss, et al. 1997; Allen and Chambers 1998; Moss and Chambers, 1999; Hall and Nichols, 2002; Bachtiar, 2004). However, inferred from Galloway and Hobday (1996) and Bhattacharya and Giosan (2003), the determination of the component of deltaic depositional system is not easy in the field.

DATA AND METHODS

Data

The Kesejahteraan and Melati outcrops is 100 to 200 meters in length and 2 to 5 meters of height are located in the northern and southern of Samarinda City (Figure 1). Those outcrops represented ancient major fluvial-wave and minor tidal process environment. Lithofacies

Figure 1 Location map of Kesejahteraan and Melati outcrops in Samarinda area. (From 2015 Google Digital Globe).

and ichnofossil data were gathered in collaboration. Ichnofossil data covered general morphology, burrow lining, bioturbation index and ichnodiversity. No paleontological information is performed.

Analyses

Ichnofacies and lithofacies data were depicted on some lithologs. Two analyses were applied. Those were ichnofacies and lithofacies analysis. Ichnofacies analysis was carried out to understand the salinity, and energy of sedimentation. Lithofacies analysis was concentrated on interpretation of the sedimentation process. Those analyses exempt from deduction model of depositional environment.

Synthesis

Synergic of ichnofacies and lithofacies analysis would comprehend the environmental quality when the sediment was deposited. The synthesis was the integration phase to resolve the particular depositional environment.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The interpretation of ancient fluvial, tidal and wave process could be conjectured from lithofacies data. Likewise, ichnofacies data could infer the salinity, energy of sedimentation in particular depositional environment. However, the collaboration of those analyses could resolve the environmental quality or paleoecolo-

Figure 2 Optimization of ichnofossil for environmental condition analysis. Black and white bar indicates stress and health condition. Blue bar indicates fairly qualitatively of salinity trend. Grey bar indicates sediment rate. Horizontal red line is *Glossifungites* ich. surface, horizontal black line is bounding discontinuity. This graphic shows the high fluctuated environmental condition. Modified from Arifullah (2005).

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Figure 3 *Ophiomorpha nodosa* is pelleted-walled traces, which generally is constructed in loose and unstable sediment. Location: Kesejahteraan outcrop Samarinda. Photograph from Arifullah (2005).

Figure 5 *Thallasinoides suevicus* is smooth-walled traces, which usually is created in soft but fairly cohesive mud or coaly shale. Location: Melati outcrop Samarinda. Photograph from Arifullah (2005).

Figure 4 *Psammichnites* (left) is grazing traces which constructed by detritus feeder. *Taenadium* (right) is meniscate back filled walled which constructed by locomotion and feeding traces near sediment surface. Location: Melati outcrop Samarinda. Photograph from Arifullah (2005).

gy that exempt from their depositional environment (Figure 2).

Arifullah (2005) had created the ichnofacies model for wave dominated delta based on ichnofacies features only (cf., Pemberton, et al. 1992). The indistinguishable ichnofacies model of Arifullah (2005) and Pemberton, et al. (1992) strongly indicated the paleontological similar factors (including the process of sedimentation) in contrasting depositional environment (deltaic versus shoreface that related to non deltaic depositional environment).

Based on Galloway and Hobday (1996) and Bhattacharya and Giosan (2003), it is a dilemma to settle

model of Arifullah (2005) and Pemberton, et al. (1992) for a wave dominated delta front or shoreface depositional environment. Definition of depositional environment accentuated by the physics, chemistry and biologic factors in place that sediment deposited (Shepard and Moore, 1955; Krumbein and Sloss, 1963; Gould, 1972; Selley, 1978; Walker, 1992; Nichols, 2009). It is clear that no relationship between paleoecological factor and place that sediment deposited. It is potentially misleading on interpretation, if lithofacies characteristic (e.g., physiogenic sedimentary structure, textures, and grain size upward trends) exclusively employed on analysis without detail ichnofossil analysis (e.g., diameter, burrow lining, bioturbation index and ichnodiversity) or vice versa. Ichnofossil is biogenic sedimentary structure which product of trace maker and sediment interaction. Style of interactions is response of physics, chemistry and biological factors (Bromley, 1996) or ecological factors (Imbrie and Newell, 1964). Ichnofossil is a powerful tool that practically utilised in the fieldwork.

Based on ichnofacies on both outcrops indicated cyclically and extremely the paleoecological change (stress versus healthy environment). The stress environment is not appropriate place for living trace maker. MacEachern, et al. (2005) suggested that highly fluctuated from paleoecological characterized by diagnostic ichnofossil features that created by opportunistic trace maker (Goldring, 1995). That features is typical of deltaic,

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lagoon and estuary depositional environment. The factor of fluvial influx regularly drive the paleoecology factors of trace maker (MacEachern, et al. 2005) such as salinity, water turbidity, temperature, etc. However based on Savrda and Bottjer (1994), factor by factor should be considered, but in reality complicated interrelationships, including positive and negative feed-back. To give an example, the effects of fluvial influx on salinity of deposits certainly affect bioturbation especially at the deltaic depositional environment.

Ichnofossil characteristics

Ichnofossil association. We have identified some ichnofossil association, such as:

1. *Ophiomorpha* association (Oph-1), includes: *Ophiomorpha nodosa* and *Skolithos*. Bioturbation index: 3 - 4, ichnodiversity (Figure 3) : 2. Lithofacies association: medium-coarse sandstone, HCS-SCS, ripple cross stratification, tangential cross stratification, and planar cross stratification.
2. *Ophiomorpha* association (Oph-2), includes: *Ophiomorpha*, *Paleophycus*, *Skolithos*, *Psammichnites*, and *Teanadium* (Figure 4). Bioturbation index: 4, ichnodiversity: 5. Lithofacies association: fine sandstone, HCS-SCS.
3. *Teichichnus* association (Te), includes, *Thalassinoides*, *Asterosoma* and *Planolites*. Bioturbation index: 4 - 5, ichnodiversity: 3 - 4. Lithofacies association: dark gray mudstone with leaf and shell fragment fossil.
4. *Thalassinoides* association (Tha-1), includes: *Thalassinoides* and *Arenicolites*. Bioturbation index: 2, ichnodiversity: 2. Lithofacies association: dark gray mudstone, lenticular-wavy laminae.
5. *Thalassinoides-Psilonichnus* association (Tha-2), includes: *Thalassinoides* and *Psilonichnus* (Figure 5). Bioturbation index: 3, ichnodiversity: 2. Lithofacies association: coal and coaly shale.
6. *Glossifungites* association (Glos-1), includes: *Thalassinoides*, *Rhizocorallium*, and *Planolites*.

Bioturbation index: 3, ichnodiversity: 3. Lithofacies association: dark gray mudstone, lenticular-wavy laminae.

Geological significance

Based on ichnofossil association analysis indicates that the ichnofossil dictated by some parameters of depositional environment, such as physical-chemical (substrate properties, sedimentation rate, energy level, light, turbidity, nutrient, salinity, oxygenation, etc) and biological factors.

Physico-chemical factors. Physico-chemical factors are related to health or stress environment (Gingras, et al. 2011). The deduction models of the relationship ichnofossil and the physico-chemical factors had published (e.g., Dastgard, et al. 2008; Pemberton and Wightman, 1992; Pemberton, et al. 1992; Ekdale, 1985; Savrda and Bottjer, 1987).

Oph-1, Oph-2 associated with fine to coarse grain size and developed an unstable and inconsistency sediment (sand migration). Sand filled passively in the tube and pelleted sand walls of *Ophiomorpha*. Other linings are formed by mucus impregnation of *Skolithos*. The strategy of burrow without linings indicates the sediments is strong enough to maintain open the burrow shaft or tunnel of *Glossifungites* (Glos-1). The burrow fill texture of *Glossifungites* is contrasted to host sediment.

Internal texture of *Teichichnus* (Te) and *Thalassinoides* (Tha) indicated that the burrow fill is meniscate or swirled or moved twisting or spiralling at soupground-softground (Ekdale, et al. 1984). This active filling is characteristic of deposit feeders mining the substrate that shows grain segregation. In this case internal grain size of burrow fill of *Teichichnus*, *Thalassinoides* and *Planolites* is more coarser than host sediment.

Ekdale (1985) had classified the *Ophiomorpha* association is created by r-selected "opportunistic" trace maker where live in variable and unpredictable environment. The r-selected exhibit high reproductive rates, rapid growth rates, broad environmental tolerance and generalized feeding habits (Pianka, 1970).

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The resolving of chemical factor based on their distribution pattern, bioturbation index and ichnodiversity. Gingras, et al. (2011) had classified the pattern of ichnofossil distribution, bioturbation index and ichnodiversity that related to physico-chemical factor. Ichnofossil association distributed sporadically and regularly heterogenous that means variable sedimentation and variable chemical stress. Lower diversity indicates the increasing physico-chemical stress. Lower bioturbation index indicates the increasing sedimentation rate.

Biological factors. Bromley (1996) describe the biological reason of animal disturbs sediment such as concealment, predation and reproduction. Byers (1982) has suggested that biological interaction is important in conjuring up morphology and distribution. Ichnofossil maybe absent because of dominance of the variety of biological factors although physico-chemical factors can stimulate potentially the trace maker. Byers (1982) has described Kitchell, et al. (1978) which the advantage of spiral morphology that minimize the risk of encountering a predator despite forage efficiency of a straight line and spiral is equivalent.

The geological significance of ichnofossil in the study area indicates that the environment related to high fluctuated and stress environmental condition (see Figure 2), rapid change and unpredictable sedimentation that proper in the tidal-wave-fluvial process environment such as deltaic environment.

CONCLUSION

Ichnofossil data elucidate potentially the physics, chemistry and biologic factors on complex depositional environment such as deltaic system. Further research along these lines should be carried out such as ichnofossil for a particular environment at any scale.

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